

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

HOW AWARE ARE PATIENT ABOUT THEIR ILLNESS BEFORE PRESENTATION TO A GENERAL OUT-PATIENT CLINIC IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL IN SOUTH-SOUTH REGION OF NIGERIA

E. M. Ebereghwa,¹ O. G. Orhe,¹ E. B. Anyanwu¹

¹Department of Family Medicine, Delta State University, P.M.B. 01, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author

E. M. Ebereghwa, Department of Family Medicine, Delta State University, P.M.B. 01, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.

Email: emebereghwa@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: In recent times, the doctor is no longer the first source of contact for health problems. Health information can be obtained from different sources, which can influence perception of medical knowledge of an individual. The study assessed how aware are patients about their illness before clinical encounter, their preferred sources of health information and the reasons for their choice.

Methodology: A cross sectional study conducted at the Family Medicine Clinic, Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara, Nigeria. Participants, aged 18 years and above were recruited using systematic random sampling method. Interviewer administered questionnaire was used to obtain data. Data was analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solution version 22.

Results: The study recruited 225 participants with the mean age of 43.42 ± 15.33 years, with more females (60.0%) than males (40.0%). Study found that 44.4% had an idea or knew something about their illness prior to consultation and 64.0% got the information from a doctor. Almost all (90.0%) the participants who knew something about their illness indicated that this influenced their decision to visit the health facility, as 72.0% reported better treatment as their reason for hospital visit while 16.9% opted for specialist opinion. Doctors were the most preferred source of health information (48.9%). This was followed by chemist/pharmacist (19.6%), nurse (9.3%) and internet (7.1%). An almost equal proportion of participants indicated easy access (44.8%) and reliable (40.0%) as the reasons for their preferred source of health information.

Conclusion: A significant number of participants had an idea or knew something about their illness prior to clinic visit. This influenced their decision to visit a doctor for better treatment. Doctors were the most preferred source of health information with an almost equal proportion of participants indicating easy access and source being reliable as the reasons for their choice. The need to understand where people seek health information in this information age is a vital step in developing optimal health information delivery and to enable doctors understand their patient's perspective.

Keywords: Aware, Health information, Illness

Introduction

How often do you have the uncanny feeling that the patient sitting across the consulting table was really searching for information from you the Physician? The patient asks questions that are subtly leading to a predetermined diagnosis.¹ Sometimes, patients suggest to the physician probable investigations to carry out, leaving the

physician with doubts over what to do.¹The probable reason is that the patient had sought information from other sources for a diagnosis prior to physician's visit.² The patient only came to confirm a self-made diagnosis.

With regards to health problems, the doctor is no longer the first source of contact, thus, the doctors' interpretation and decision-making authority over

medical questions competes with other sources consulted by the patient.¹ Also, in recent times, medical consultation process involves the interaction between the physician and the patient who agree on a shared decision-making path.³ Putting all these together, it is imperative that physicians understand patient's ideas, concerns and expectations that are influenced by the sources of health information that the patient have consulted prior to their encounter with the physician.³ As failure to recognize these factors may result in impaired doctor-patient relationship such as eroded trust in the doctor, longer clinical consultations resulting from disagreement over information given by patient and unnecessary tests and treatments arising from information and can make the doctor to feel anxious and challenged.^{1,4} Over the last decade, medical knowledge has been unleashed, flowing as information through a myriad of electronic networks and internet sources.⁵ Health information is any appropriate health and health related information such as causes and symptoms, diagnosis of diseases, treatment and prevention of diseases which is the main worry of most people.^{6,7} With the increasing availability of internet access, a shift has been observed in the pattern in which patients obtain health information from the traditional sources to using the internet.³ This has allowed patients to have unlimited access and interpretation of information about disease ahead of their encounter with the doctor.⁵

Globally, seeking for health information is an emerging phenomenon.⁸ In the United States of America (USA), about seventy-two percent of adults searched the internet for health information and more than thirty-three percent of them sought the internet for self-diagnosis.⁹ Health information seeking is defined as the search for and receipt of messages that help "to reduce uncertainty regarding health status" and "construct a social and personal (cognitive) sense of health".¹⁰ Several factors such as increase in the incidence of certain diseases, inadequate knowledge on health-related conditions and insufficient time for consultation with health care professionals have been identified as reasons that prompt patients to seek health information apart from the health care system.⁶ Patients knowledge of disease consists of beliefs founded on information on the different aspects of the disease obtained both before and

after the diagnosis.¹¹ These beliefs are related to the causes of the disease, aggravating factors, recognition of symptoms, available treatment options and complications.¹¹ These ideas on disease are obtained from various sources like clinche' concerning a given disease, previous personal experiences, medical personnel, books or the internet.¹¹ However, the accuracy of the beliefs/ ideas may vary and in fact some are wrong.¹¹

Furthermore, health information can be obtained from different sources, which can influence perception of medical knowledge of an individual.¹² Sources of health information can be grouped into print materials (books, newspaper, journal, brochure), non-print materials (radio, television, internet), health specialists (discussion with health care professionals) and interpersonal sources (discussion with family, relatives and friends).¹³ Also, it can be classified into online and offline sources.¹⁴ The offline sources include health care professionals, mass media, health books, journal, friends, family members and use of local experts (persons who have appreciable experience in health care profession or persons who once experienced the medical problem).¹⁵ Commonly, used sources of health information are the internet, physicians, social media, radio and television, pharmacists and parents.¹² Having a reliable source of health information is fundamental and will form the bedrock on which the public knowledge of health information is built, particularly with the recent revolution in the internet and social media.¹²

In addition, there is need for Physicians to understand where and why people go in search for information. As knowledge of the various sources from where health information is sought by patients could have an impact on the quality of health care rendered and could influence patients' judgement of a Physician's medical opinion and so affect their health decision-making.¹² Also, the need to understand how people seek health information in this information age is a vital step in developing optimal health information delivery and to enable doctors understand their patient's perspective.^{16,17} Furthermore, healthcare professionals can guide their patients to accurate and reliable sources of information or they can better educate their patients about the disease or problem they may be having.¹⁶ Thus, the study

aimed to assess how aware are patients seen in the general out-patient clinic in a tertiary hospital in South-South Nigeria about their illness before clinical encounter, their preferred sources of health information and the reasons for their choice.

Methods

The study was carried out at the Family Medicine Clinic of Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELTH), Oghara, Nigeria. DELSUTH is a renowned 180-bed ultra-modern teaching hospital with many clinical specialties, situated in Oghara, Ethiope West Local Government Area of Delta State, South-South Nigeria. It is one of the two tertiary health institutions providing healthcare service to Delta indigenes and its adjoining states. It provides primary, secondary and tertiary care to the populace. This is a hospital based cross-sectional.

Study population: These are all adult patients (age 18 years and above) attending the Family Medicine Clinic in Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara. Clinical records of the Family medicine clinic reported that a total of 5,023 adult patients attended the Family Medicine clinic in the year 2022.

Inclusion criteria

Participants included in the study were adults age 18 years and above willing to participate in the study with the ability to give informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

Participants excluded from the study were critically ill patients and patients unwilling to participate.

Study duration

It was conducted from September to November, 2023 (three month duration).

Sample size determination and sampling method

The sample size was determined using a single population proportion formula, $n = z^2 pq/d^2$,¹⁸ using z as 95% of confidence level, d as 5% margin of error and p was the estimated proportion with the attribute of interest which was 24.8% obtained from a previous study¹⁹ and n the minimum sample size was 287. Since the number of patients seen in the clinic in the previous year was less than 10,000 (5023), the sample size was adjusted by the formula; $nf = n/(1 + n/N)$ ¹⁸, where, n was the desired sample size when the population is more than 10,000 which was 287, and N was

population of patients aged 18 years old and above(5023). Thus, nf was the desired sample size when the population is less than 10,000, calculated to be 272. Therefore, the minimum sample size was 272.

The study participants were recruited using systematic random sampling method. Using $K = N/n$,¹⁸ where K was the sampling interval, N was the sampling frame (5023 patients aged 18 years and above were seen in 12months, then 1256 patients were seen in 3 months) and n was 272. A sampling interval of 5 was obtained. The first subject was selected by simple random and every 5th participants was selected by systematic random sampling until the required sample size was met.

Data collection method

A pretested interviewer administered questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire was adopted from previous studies,^{9,15,20,21} and consists of sociodemographic characteristics, questions related to having knowledge of their illness prior to presentation to the hospital and from who/ where the information was obtained, did the information influence their decision to visit the hospital and will they discuss information with the doctor. Also, participants preferred source of health information was sought and reasons for choosing the source of health information.

Data management

Data was entered into excel spreadsheet and coded into the Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS) version 22 (IBM, Chicago) for analysis. Demographic variables and categorical variables were presented using frequency tables as appropriate. Continuous variables such as age were presented using means and standard deviation.

Ethical consideration

Approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara with approval number; HREC/PAN/2023/050/0581. Informed consent was obtained from all the participants before data collection. All information was treated confidentially and participants could withdraw at any point without prejudice to their future care.

Results

Two hundred and seventy-two participants were recruited in the study, forty-seven were excluded

due to incomplete data, leaving a total of two hundred and twenty-five participants and a response rate of 82.7%.

The mean age of participants was 43.42 ± 15.33 , with half (54.2%) within the age range of 18 to 44 years old. There were more females (60.0%) than males (40.0%) and nearly half (46.2%) had tertiary education. (Table 1)

One hundred (44.4%) of the participants had an idea or knew something about their illness prior to consultation with nearly two-third (64.0%) obtaining the information from a doctor. Almost all (90.0%) the participants who knew something about their illness indicated that this influenced their decision to visit the health facility, as about three-quarter (72.0%) reported better treatment as their reason for presentation to the hospital while a little less than one-fifth (16.9%) opted for specialist opinion. Also, nearly all (97.0%) the participants who had information about their illness were willing tell their doctor. (Table 2)

Doctor was the most preferred source of health information for about half (48.9%) of the participants. This was followed by chemist/pharmacist (19.6%) and nurse (9.3%). However, very few participants (7.1%) indicated the internet as their preferred source of health information. (Table 3)

An almost equal proportion of participants indicated easy access (44.8%) and reliable (40.0%) as the reasons for their preferred source of health information. However, very few (7.1%) chose improve understanding of specific health problem as the reason for their preferred source of health information. (Table 4).

Discussion

The study aimed to assess how aware are patients about their illness before presentation, their preferred sources of health information and the reasons for their choice in order to create awareness among physicians of other sources of health information accessed by patients and to encourage them to educate and guide their patients to accurate and reliable sources of health information thereby promoting better patient-doctor relationship and patient satisfaction.

An understanding of patients' primary source of health information is necessary as first information obtained can provide patients with the required knowledge for further search.²² This can also play a vital role in influencing patients'

beliefs about the health condition and the decision about the healthcare that follows.²² Also, seeking of health information have been found to influence health knowledge, self-efficacy and awareness.²³ Less than half of the participants had an idea or knew something about their illness prior to consultation. A study in Iran noted that one-third of participants searched for information from different sources in order to have awareness of their health issues prior to visiting a physician.¹³ A cross-sectional study done in Saudi Arabia revealed that older adult searched for information on the cause of their illness from various health information sources.²⁴ Also, more than half obtained the information about their illness from a doctor. In contrast, two-third of participants was reported to have sought information from other sources prior to a doctor's visit in a study conducted in Saudi Arabia.¹² This finding is not surprising, as the study was conducted in a tertiary health institution which served as a referral center in the state. Therefore, many of the patients seen in the facility would have visited either a primary or secondary healthcare facility where they would have been told about their illness by a doctor, who may have probably referred them to our facility. However, it is important to note that over one-third of the participants got the information about their illness from other sources such as the patent medicine vendors, nurses, internet and family members. Some of these sources may not be accurate and reliable, hence the need for doctors to seek to know patients' knowledge of their illness and the sources where it was obtained, so as to correct, educate and provide accurate health information to patients.

When people are ill, there is a desire to know the cause of their illness, hence the quest for information from different sources which can influence their medical decision making process.²⁵ Almost all the participants who knew something about their illness indicated that this influenced their decision to visit the health facility, as about three-quarter reported better treatment as their reason for presentation to the hospital while a little less than one-fifth opted for specialist opinion. A study in Lagos, Nigeria reported that many of the individuals who used the social media to seek for medical information had to make specific referral to a physician following the search.²⁶

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of participants.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
<18	1	0.4
18-44	122	54.2
45-64	74	32.9
≥ 65	28	12.4
Mean age	43.42±15.33	
Gender		
Male	90	40.0
Female	135	60.0
Educational Level		
None	9	4.0
Primary	41	18.2
Secondary	71	31.6
Tertiary	104	46.2

Table 2: Patients' awareness of their illness prior to clinic visit.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Know the name/diagnosis of the illness that brought them to the hospital		
Yes	100	44.4
No	125	55.6
From who/where did you get the information about your illness (n = 100)		
Doctor	64	64.0
Nurse	11	11.0
Internet	4	4.0
Family members	4	4.0
Friends	3	3.0
Chemist/Pharmacist	13	13.0
Tradomedical centre	1	1.0
Did this influence your decision to come here? (n = 100)		
Yes	90	90.0
No	10	10.0
Would you tell the doctor the information you got about your illness? (n = 100)		
No	3	3.0
Yes	97	97.0
Why did you come to our facility?		
For better treatment	162	72.0
For more investigation	24	10.7
To prove what I had been told before	1	0.4
For specialist opinion	38	16.9

Table 3: Preferred source of health information.

Source of health information.	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Doctor	110	48.9
Nurse	21	9.3
Internet	16	7.1
Family members	18	8.0
Friends	10	4.4
Chemist/Pharmacist	44	19.6
Tradomedical center	5	2.2
Pastor/Imam	1	0.4

Table 4: Reasons for using source of health information.

Reasons	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Easy access	101	44.8
User anonymity	4	1.8
Reliable	90	40.0
Recommended by family/friends	14	6.2
Improve understanding of specific health problem	16	7.1

Furthermore, the study revealed that doctors were the most preferred source of health information. Similar finding was reported in previous studies.^{12,27} In contrast, studies in Adamawa, Nigeria and Iran reported the mass media (television and radio) as the most preferred source of health information.^{13,28} Of note is the use of chemist/pharmacists as the second preferred source of health information in this study. This might not be surprising as previous studies in Nigeria reported that majority of participants sought healthcare from patent medicine vendors.^{29,30} They were described as a more accessible and affordable source of healthcare service.^{29,30} Also, the owners of patent medicine stores live within the community and so are well known by their clients.^{29, 30} This relationship is thought to facilitate easy communication in many relatively poor communities in Nigeria.^{29,30} This perception may have accounted for this source as the second common source of health information in this study. Interestingly, only very few participants identified the internet as their preferred source of health information. Although, this finding was in congruent with some previous studies in Nigeria.^{6,15,31} This may be attributed to concerns raised about the trustworthiness of the source of information, as it has been identified as a major determinant that influence frequency of use and value of a source of health information.³²

Looking for health information is a complex process affected by a variety of factors.³³ An almost equal proportion of participants indicated easy access and reliable as the reasons for their preferred source of health information. However, very few chose improve understanding of specific health problem as the reason for their preferred source of health information. A study carried out in Egypt reported easy access and improving understanding of a specific health problem as the most common reasons for choosing preferred source of health information.²¹ The finding in this study may be accounted for by the participants most preferred source of health information as doctors. Physicians have been described as the most reliable and a very important source of access to health information.²³ Similar finding was noted in Saudi Arabia where doctors were chosen as the most trusted source of health information.¹² Majority preferred to seek help from doctors as they did not trust the information obtained from social media.¹² Also, the study reported that participants disagreed with replacing a doctor's prescription with information obtained from the internet or a friend or relative.¹²

Conclusion

A significant number of participants had an idea or knew something about their illness prior to clinic visit. This influenced their decision to visit a doctor for better treatment. Doctors were the

most preferred source of health information with an almost equal proportion of participants indicating easy access and source being reliable as the reasons for their choice. The need to understand where people seek health information in this information age is a vital step in developing optimal health information delivery and to enable doctors understand their patient's perspective. Thus, doctors can better educate their patients about the disease or problem they may be having and guide their patients to other accurate and reliable sources of information. This can promote better patient-doctor relationship and lead to patient dissatisfaction.

Acknowledgment

Authors sincerely appreciate all the patients that participated in this study and also appreciate the staff of the Family medicine clinic of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara, Nigeria.

Declarations

Funding

Funding was by authors.

Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests

None

Code availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Authors' Contributions

EEM and AEB were involved in the conceptualization of the research problem, literature review and research design; EEM did the data collection, entry and analysis; EEM, AEB and OOG were involved in the drafting of the manuscript for submission and revision of final draft.

Ethics approval

The study was conducted after approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara with approval number; HREC/PAN/2023/050/0581.

Consent to participate

Informed consent was obtained from all the participants before data collection and participants

could withdraw at any point without prejudice to their future care

Consent for publication

Authors have accepted responsibility for the entire content of this manuscript and approved its submission and publication.

References

1. Wangler J, Jansky M. General practitioners' challenges and strategies in dealing with internet-related health anxieties- results of a qualitative study among primary care physicians in Germany. *Wien Med Wochenschr.* 2020; 170:329-339.
2. Tan SL, Goonawardene N. Internet health information seeking and the patient-physician relationship: a systematic review. *J Med Internet Res.* 2017;19(1): e9. doi: 10.2196/jmir.5729.
3. Kyriacou A, Sherratt C. Online health information-seeking behaviour by endocrinology patients. *Hormones.* 2019; 18: 495-505.
4. Russ H, Giveon S, Catarivas M, Yaphe J. The effect of the internet on the patient-doctor relationship from the patient's perspective: a survey from primary care. *IMAJ.* 2011; 13: 220-224.
5. Jutel A. Self-Diagnosis: a discursive systematic review of the medical literature. *J Participat Med.* 2010; 2: 1-13.
6. Abedoh GO, Udoudoh SJ, Babalola GA. Health information seeking behaviour and utilization for the management of diabetes mellitus among patients in two federal medical centres in North Central, Nigeria. *Information Technology and Librarianship.* 2022; 2: 86-99.
7. Dastani M, Mokhtarzadeh M, Nasirzadeh A, Delshad A. Health information seeking behaviour among students of Gonabad university of medical sciences. *Library Philosophy and Practice.* 2019; 1: 1-11.
8. Farnood A, Johnston B, Mair F. A mixed methods systematic review of the effects of patient online self-diagnosing in the 'smart-phone society' on the healthcare professional-patient relationship and medical authority. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making.* 2020; 20: 253-267.
9. Ali AA, Fardan FA, Aljamri SZ, Salman WM, Mandeel MA, Bahram S. Online health information seeking among patients attending

primary care clinics in Bahrain: a cross sectional study. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2022; 10(10): 2086-2099.

10. Cotton SR, Gupta SS. Characteristics of online and online health information seekers and factors that discriminate between them. *Social Science & Medicine.* 2004; 59: 1795-1806.

11. Szymona-Palkowska K, Janowski K, Pedrycz A, Mucha D, Ambrozy T, Siermontowski P *et al.* Knowledge of the disease, perceived social support and cognitive appraisals in women with urinary incontinence. *BioMed Research International.* 2016; 1: 1-7.

12. Alduraywish SA, Altamimi LA, Aldhuwayhi RA, AlZamil LR, Alzeghayer LY, Alsaleh FS *et al.* Sources of health information and their impacts on medical knowledge perception among the Saudi Arabian population: cross sectional study. *J Med Internet Res.* 2020; 22(3): 1-9.

13. Gavgani V, Qeisari E, Jafarabadi M. Health information seeking behaviour (HISB): a study of a developing country. *Library Philosophy and Practice.* 2013; 1: 902-931.

14. Liu L. Medical information seeking behaviour of urban patients in Zhejiang province, China: a cross sectional study. *BMC Public Health.* 2022; 22: 1591-1603.

15. Akpoghiran ID. Communication source of seeking health information among women: a study in Orerokpe, Delta state, Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Social Sciences.* 2020; 6(1): 319-328.

16. Gass M. Risks and benefits of self-diagnosis using the internet. (thesis) Salem State University[Internet]. 2016 [cited July 20 2023]: 1-20. Available from: <https://hdl.handle.net/20.50013013/897>

17. Rao N, Tighe E, Feinberg I. The dispersion of health information-seeking behaviour and health literacy in a state in the Southern United States: cross sectional study. *JMIR Form Res*[Internet]. 2022[cited July 20 2023]; 6(6): e34708. Available from: <https://formative.jmir.org/2022/6/e34708>.

18. Araoye MO. Subject selection. In: Parakoyi B, editor. *Research methodology with statistics for health and social sciences.* 2nd Ed. Ilorin: Nathadex publishers; 2004.115-129.

19. Etukumana A, Egwuda L, Chukwudi J, Andem N, Udoh G. Internet use among primary care patients attending a tertiary health facility in

Uyo, South-south, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Family Practice.* 2016; 7(4).

20. Yilma TM, Inthiran A, Reidpath D, Orimaye SO. Health information seeking and its associated factors among university students: a case in a middle-income setting. *PACIS 2017 Proceedings*[Internet]. 2017[cited Jan 21 2024]; 265. Available from: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/pacis2017/265>.

21. Ghweeba M, Lindenmeyer A, Shishi S, Abbas M, Waheed A, Amer S. What predicts online health information-seeking behaviour among Egyptian adults? A cross sectional study. *J Med Internet Res*[Internet]. 2017[cited Jan 21 2024]; 19(6): e216. Available from: <https://www.jmir.org/2017/6/e216>.

22. Jiang S, Basnyat I, Liu P. Factors influencing internet health information seeking in India: an application of the comprehensive model of information seeking. *International journal of Communication.* 2021; 15: 2047-2068.

23. Simou E. Health information sources: trust and satisfaction. *International Journal of Healthcare.* 2016;2(1):38-43.

24. Agyemang-Duah W, Arthur-Holmes F, Peprah C, Adei D, Peprah P. Dynamics of health information-seeking behaviour among older adults with very low incomes in Ghana: a qualitative study. *BMC Public Health.* 2020; 20: 928-941.

25. Mehra P. Face to face information seeking behaviour of patients and impact on in-clinic satisfaction. *Asia Pacific Management Review.* 2015; 20: 293-303.

26. Odiboh O, Omokiti O, Ekanem T, Oyedepo T. The perception of patients on healthcare information and social media in suburban primary healthcare centres, Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of e-health Management.* 2022; 1: 1-16.

27. Anyoaku EN, Nwosu OC. Extent of access to health information and sources for chronic disease patients in tertiary health institutions in South East Nigeria: implications for libraries role. *Library Philosophy and Practice*[Internet]. 2017[cited Jan 22 2024]; 1504. Available from: <https://digitalcommons.edu/libphilprac/1504>.

28. Mathias H, Shuaibu U, Umar B. An assessment of health information seeking behaviour of rural dwellers in Lala and Ga'anda

emirate councils in Gombi local government in Adamawa state, Nigeria. *Jewel Journal of Librarianship*. 2021; 16(3):177-187.

29. Olasehinde N. Healthcare seeking behaviour in Nigeria. *Journal of Population and Social Studies*. 2018;26(3):207-218. doi: 10.25133/JPSSv26n3.015.

30. Okojie PW, Lane R. Health care options and factors influencing health seeking behaviour in a rural community in Nigeria: a cross-sectional study. *Christian Journal for Global Health*. 2020;7(2):83-92.

31. Ezeh C, Ezeh O. Perception and information seeking behaviour of rural households towards health promoting practices in Maigana district of Kaduna state, Nigeria. *Open Journal of Medical Psychology*. 2017; 6: 233-242.

32. Adegbilero-Iwari OE, Oluwadare T, Adegbilero-Iwari I. A cross-sectional survey of online health information seeking behaviour pattern of undergraduate students in a Nigerian private university. *Library Philosophy and Practice*[Internet]. 2021[cited Jan 23 2024];5787. Available from: <https://digitalcommons.uni.edu/libphilprac/5787>.

33. Yigzaw K, Wynn R, Marco-Ruiz L, Budrionis A, Oyeyemi S, Fagerlund A *et al*. The association between health information seeking on the internet and physician visits (The seventh Tromso study- part 4): population-based questionnaire study. *J Med Internet Res*[Internet]. 2020[cited 2024[cited Jan 23 2024]; 22(3): e13120. Available from: <https://www.jmir.org/2020/3/e13120>.